

A CLINICAL AUDIT OF THE SUCCESS RATE OF REMOVABLE FUNCTIONAL APPLIANCES TREATMENT

Mohd Zambri Mohamed Makhbul¹, Wan Nurazreena Wan Hassan²

¹Orthodontic Unit, Klinik Pergigian Cahaya Suria, Bangunan Pudu Sentral, Jalan Pudu, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.

²Department of Paediatric Dentistry and Orthodontics Research Group, Faculty of Dentistry, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.

ABSTRACT

Aims:

This audit aimed to determine the common timing of treatment with twin block appliance, the success rate within the first 6 months of treatment and possible reasons of failure of twin block appliances treatment at a government orthodontic clinic in Kuala Lumpur.

Methods:

Class II division 1 patients treated with twin block appliances from the year 2014 to 2016 were assessed. The treatment was deemed successful if the overjet had reduced by at least 50% within the first 6 months of treatment. If the overjet had not reduced by 10% within 6 months of treatment, patients were classed as non-compliant. Inter-operator reliability for assessing the cervical vertebral maturation (CVM) was confirmed using intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC). Two standards were set, which included 100% of cases should start at CVM stage 3 or 4 and 100% of twin block functional appliance treatment should be successful.

Results:

Forty-five samples were included. Majority of the patients had their treatment started at CVM 4 (51.1%), followed by CVM 3 (26.7%) and CVM 5 (15.6%). One patient had treatment started early at CVM 2. Two patients' CVM could not be determined as the cervical spine was cut off from the radiographic films. Of all patients included, 28 (62.2%) were successful and 16 (35.6%) were non-compliant.

Among the 29 compliant subjects, one who was not successful had broken lower appliance. Among the non-compliant patients, seven (43.8%) had broken lower appliances and three (18.8%) did not attend the follow-up appointments. The mean pre-treatment overjet was 10.25mm (SD2.21) and post-treatment overjet was 3.13mm (SD 1.73). The mean differences of 7.13mm (SD 2.17) were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$; 95%CI =6.28-7.97).

Conclusion:

Twin block appliances treatment were effective to reduce the overjet. Nonetheless, the standards set were not met. There is a need to address the problems relating to poor compliance such as improve laboratory work quality or offer alternative treatments.

Keywords

Functional appliances, Twin block appliances, Class II division 1, Cervical vertebral maturation

Introduction

Class II malocclusion is a common problem and the treatment depends on the aetiology of malocclusion. Patients usually present with a main concern of increased overjet. Skeletal Class II malocclusion can result from maxillary protrusion, mandibular retrusion, or combination of the two (1). The most common aetiology of angle Class II dentoskeletal disharmony malocclusion in orthodontic patients is mandibular retrognathia (2).

Those with increased overjet are recommended to be treated early to reduce the potential trauma on the incisors (3), especially since young children have the tendency to fall and knock their teeth. Class II malocclusion can be treated by camouflage orthodontics, growth modification and orthognathic surgery. However, in growing patients, the functional appliance has been proven to produce a combination of dental and skeletal effects to reduce the overjet (4). The optimal treatment timing for growth modification is during pubertal growth spurt (5). The pubertal growth spurt can be determined with cervical vertebral maturation (CVM) method (6), which can be assessed using the lateral cephalometric radiograph. Using this method, the peak pubertal growth is expected to be between the cervical stages (CS) CS3 and CS4 (6).

There are several types of functional appliances, which are namely divided into two categories: the fixed and removable functional appliances (7). The primary difference between them is the premium on compliance with removable whilst full-time wear is guaranteed with the fixed type (8). The twin block appliance is one of the most commonly used functional appliances, partly due to its acceptability by patients (9) and cost. The twin block has been shown to reduce the overjet with some potential to enhance the mandibular growth (10). Since it is a removable type of appliance, one of the important criteria for the successful treatment outcome is good cooperation or compliance from the patient.

At the orthodontic unit, Klinik Pergigian Cahaya Suria, Kuala Lumpur, the twin block is commonly prescribed among the adolescent Class II patients. It is hoped that by taking advantage of early correction during peak pubertal growth spurt, we may be

able avoid the potential need for orthognathic surgery. However, failures have been noted and some of these patients ended with orthognathic surgery in order to correct the overjet and Class II skeletal pattern. The purpose of this audit is to determine the common timing of treatment with twin block appliance, the success rate of twin block functional appliance treatment and to investigate possible reasons of treatment failure.

Methods

This retrospective audit was registered with the Malaysian National Institute of Health Research (ID Number: 35113). The sample consisted of patients treated with twin block functional appliance by a single operator from year 2014 until 2016. The inclusion criteria were patients who were less than 17 years old at the start of treatment, Class II division 1 malocclusion and the pre-treatment overjet was greater than 5.0mm, Class II molar relationships, fully erupted premolars and canines at start of treatment and follow up of examination at least 6 months after wearing twin block functional appliance. The exclusion criteria were history of asymmetric extractions or aplasia of permanent teeth and craniofacial syndromes or severe facial asymmetry.

The pre-treatment CVM stage was determined by a single operator (MZMM) and the inter-examiner reliability was done with another operator (WNWH) based on absolute agreement of 29 samples selected in an aleatory way.

The records were assessed for the pre-treatment CVM stage, pre-treatment overjet and overjet at 6 months. Any problems recorded in the case notes were also identified. All patients were seen by the same operator (MZMM) who measured the overjets clinically and recorded the values and other findings in the case notes. The patients diagnosed with Class II Division 1 and indicated for functional appliances treatment had their appliances issued within 6 months after the records taken.

If the overjet has not reduced by 10% within 6 months the patient was classed as not compliant (10). Thus, if the overjet was reduced by more than 10%, the patient was considered compliant. The treatment was considered successful if the overjet was reduced by a minimum of 50% (10).

The standards set for this audit were:

- For cost-effectiveness reasons, 100% of functional appliance treatment should be successful.
- For optimal care, 100% of functional appliance treatment should start at CVM CS3 or CS4 (6).

The data was analyzed with SPSS (version 20). Paired t-test was used to compare the overjet changes.

Result

Fifty patients were identified to have had twin block appliances during the audit period but five were excluded because they had less than six months follow up period. Subjects comprised 19 (42%) boys and 26 (58%) girls. The inter-operator reliability for the CVM assessment was excellent, with ICC at 0.97 (p<0.05). Table 1 shows the distribution of cases according to their CVM. Majority of the patients had their treatment started at CVM CS4 (51.1%), followed by CVM CS3 (26.7%) and CVM CS5 (15.6%). One patient had treatment started early at CVM CS2 (2.2%). Two patients' CVM could not be determined as the cervical spine was cut off from the radiographic films. The proportion of successful treatment decline with increasing CVM start stages; the single patient (100%) who started treatment at CVM CS2 were successful, 10 out of 13 patients (83.3%) who started treatment at CVM CS3, 13 out of 23 patients (56.5%) who started treatment at CVM CS4 and 3 out of 7 patients (42.9%) who started treatment at CVM CS5 were successful.

Table 1: Cervical vertebral maturation stages of patients at the start of treatment

CVM stages	Compliant	Non-compliant			TOTAL
	Successful	<i>Compliant</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>With</i>	<i>DNA</i>
		<i>but not</i>	<i>excuse</i>	<i>excuse</i>	
		<i>successful</i>			

2	1					1 (2.2%)
3	10	1	1			12 (26.7%)
4	13		4	5	1	23 (51.1%)
5	3		1	1	2	7 (15.6%)
Undetermined	1		1			2 (4.4%)

Italics are unsuccessful category, DNA : Did not attend

Table 2 shows the outcome of the 45 samples were included in the audit. Of these, 28 (62.2%) were found successful and 16 (35.6%) were not compliant. Among the 29 (64.4%) compliant subjects, one of those who were not successful had broken lower appliance. Among the non-compliant patients, seven (43.8%) had broken lower appliances and three (18.8%) did not attend the follow-up appointments.

Table 2: Compliance and success rates of functional appliances

	N	(%of total)	n (% of N)	Reasons
Compliant (OJ reduced >10%)	29	(64.4%)		
Successful (OJ reduced >50%)	28	(96.6%)		
Compliant but not successful (OJ reduced >10% but <50%)	1	(3.4%)		Broken lower appliances

Non-compliant (OJ reduced <10%)	16 (35.6%)	
No excuse	6 (37.5%)	
With excuse	7 (43.8%)	Broken appliances
Did not attend appointment (OJ assumed no change)	3 (18.8%)	

Table 3 shows the comparison between the pre- and post-treatment overjet of the successful cases. The mean pretreatment overjet was 10.25mm (SD2.21) and post-treatment overjet of 3.13mm (SD 1.73). The mean differences were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$; 95%CI did not include zero).

Table 3: Comparison between before and after treatment of the successful cases

	Mean	SD	Mean differences (SD)	95% CI		p value
				Lower	Upper	
Pre-treatment	10.25	2.21	7.13 (2.17)	6.28	7.97	0.00*
Post-treatment	3.13	1.73				

* $p < 0.001$

Discussion

Twin block appliance treatment have anecdotally been associated with treatment failures. The aim of this audit was to identify the percentage of successful twin block functional appliance in a local Malaysian setting. The gold standards were set according to previous studies (6, 10) and should be the benchmark to achieve the target of successful results for twin block functional appliance.

Functional appliance is effective during the pubertal growth spurt and this can be observed from the CVM stages in the lateral cephalometric radiograph. The CVM method is a reproducible and reliable method to assess the mandibular growth (11). Previous study suggested that even though the validity and reliability of the CVM method proved statistically acceptable but many other growth indicators should be taken into consideration in evaluating adolescent skeletal maturation (12). In addition, peak-standing height may be used in routine clinical practice to enhance efficiency of treatments requiring identification of the mandibular growth spurt (13).

CVM CS3 and CS4 are the optimal timing for growth modification since the peak in mandibular growth is expected to occur during the year after CVM CS3 or to have had occurred within 1 or 2 years before CVM CS4 (6). The peak in mandibular growth is expected to occur 1 year after CVM CS2, or has ended at least 1 year before CVM CS5 (6), thus stages other than CVM CS3 and CS4 are considered too early or too late for growth modification treatment. Supplementary mandibular elongation is more when the growth spurt is included in the treatment interval than when treatment is done before the peak in mandibular growth (6), indicating that treatment that do not optimize the peak in mandibular growth are expected to induce more dentoalveolar changes rather than growth modification.

In this is audit, the standard for starting treatment at CVM CS3 or CS4 was 100%. However, the standard was not met, with only 82 percent of patients who started treatment at CVM CS3 or CS4. This standard was not met because the single patient, who started treatment at CVM CS2, was referred early and justified for treatment to prevent trauma to the upper incisors and address any low self-esteem effect from being teased due to prominent front teeth at school. That patient was compliant, and the treatment was found successful, supporting the benefit for treating the patient early. For older patients, who were in CVM CS5, treatment was still

attempted to reduce the overjet with twin block functional appliances because these patients refused orthognathic surgery and were willing to persevere with twin block appliances treatment. Nonetheless, only three out of the seven patients who started the treatment at CVM CS5 were compliant and successful. With a low success rate of 42.9%, the removable twin block appliances may not be a cost-effective treatment for Class II Division 1 patients who first attended at CVM CS5. Alternative treatments should be considered such as with fixed-functional appliances for these patients.

The success rate of the twin block functional appliance was measured by overjet reduction after 6 months of treatment (10). Failure rates with twin-block appliances ranged from 25% to 34% (14-17). In spite of this, the standard for success with functional appliance in this audit was set at an ideal standard of 100% for cost-effectiveness reasons. In practice, poor success would incur costs as expenses spent to construct the appliances have been wasted and further alternatives need to be offered. The setting of the current audit had access to in-house technicians, making twin block appliance the cheaper choice compared to commercially manufactured fixed-functional appliances such as Forsus Fatigue Resistant Devices. The current audit suggests for alternatives to the removable twin block appliances, which has compliance issues in select group of patients. It may be justifiable to offer the more expensive fixed-functional treatment, which is less likely to have compliance issues, to older adolescent patients who first attended treatment at the later CVM stages.

The standard set was not met as only 62 percent (N=28) of twin block treatment was classified as successful. The success rate of the twin block depends on the compliance and this audit reported that 64.4 percent patient compliance towards the twin block treatment. Broken lower twin blok appliance was the most frequently reported reason for unsuccessful treatment or poor compliance in this audit. This suggest that there is a need to recommend reassessment in the lower appliance design to avoid treatment failure. Broken appliance affects duration of appliance. Since success is defined by overjet reduction within a 6 months period from the day the appliance was first issued, the cases had lower chances for success since active treatment time was reduced. The patients would not be using the twin block appliances during the broken, repair or replacement period. Failure to attend the follow up treatment was another factor contributing to poor success rates or

compliance. The reason for not coming for appointments was not known. Follow up by phone call is recommended to understand the reason for not continuing treatment. Six patients (37.5%) did not report any reason for poor compliance. It is possible that they have not been wearing the appliance well. The appliance design may also be a factor of the patient acceptance since aesthetic design encourages patients to wear the appliances full time (18). The twin block appliance, being a bulky appliance, may not appeal in design, which in turn reduces compliance. Alternatively, compliance can be monitored using indicators such as the TheraMon® sensor which is embedded in the acrylic. This has been shown to contribute to better patient compliance (19), but adding such sensor may add to the cost of the appliance.

Among the successful patients, the post-treatment overjet reduced to 3.13mm, which indicated that the post-treatment overjet returned to the ideal normal overjet range of 2-4mm. The mean of overjet reduction was statistically significant, which supports the effectiveness of twin block appliance for overjet reduction. Previous study reported the successful twin block treatment was 84 percent and the highest success rate was when treatment started at CS3 or CS4, which was 94 percent (20). This audit and previous audit (20) showed that the CS3 or CS4 were suitable time to start the treatment of twin block functional appliance.

Conclusion

The standards set were not met. However, the twin block appliance was effective in the reduction of the overjet. There is a need to improve the success rates and patient compliance towards the treatment. There is a need to address the problems relating to poor compliance such as improve laboratory work quality or offer alternative treatments.

Recommendation

- i. Appliance design for the lower twin block may need to be modified in order to reduce the frequency of broken appliances.
- ii. Patient compliance need to be improved. This may include suggestion to add compliant monitoring device to the appliance or to consider using fixed-functional appliances.

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